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URBAN ECO-SUSTAINABILITY AND DISASTER RISK REDUCTION BY IMPLEMENTING VERTICAL GARDEN IN DHAKA CITY

Md. Habibur Rahman¹, Tasnim Zafar Khan², Rakib Ahmed Raju³, Muhammad Jahedul Huq⁴

ABSTRACT

Green space in Dhaka city is reducing day by day and affecting urban eco-systems producing multi-dimensional socio economic, cultural and environmental problems. In this scenario, we argue that vertical garden could be a way to mitigate these urban problems. Though vertical gardening is not a new concept in Bangladesh, it has emerged recently because of its diverse uses like reducing the hostile ecological effect of the buildings and greenhouse gas emission, air purification, regulating the temperature and rainfall runoff, providing food and wildlife habitat, as well as creating employment and recreational opportunities. Therefore, the study aims to evaluate the practices of vertical gardening contributing to eco-sustainability and disaster risk reduction in the context of the Dhaka city. Following qualitative approach, the study performed in-depth interviews, participant observation and visual documentation as data collection tools in order to understand contemporary practices and types of vertical gardening, and ecosystem services produced by vertical garden. This study attempts to review the major opportunities and challenges of vertical gardening, through the framework of eco-system services and urban resilience.

Keywords: Vertical Garden, Eco-system services, Disaster Risk Reduction, Urban resilience

Introduction

Urban growth is estimated to increase rapidly in the coming decades. Thus cities will face new and ongoing challenges in case of environment, economic, education, health, food etc. Urban areas are major players in striving for carbon free economic growth and at the same time helping their populations to deal with climate uncertainty and natural disasters. Usually urban areas are characterized by materials of low porosity and shortage of evapo-transpiring surfaces (vegetation). In addition, human activities are also responsible for anthropogenic heat release. Urban areas are riskier than rural areas in case of hazards because of its complex, sophisticated nature and population density. All governments are committed to protect their citizens and resilience can be a public good in this regard (Lall, et al. 2009).

Over the last 50 years, more than 40% the green space was lost due to the development of infrastructure, housing, etc. (Kabir et al. 2018). Clean-Green Dhaka is a Campaign introduced by DNCC which aims to make the city clean and green with integrated effort. As a part of this campaign, more buildings practice rooftop gardening today. City dwellers get a chance contribute to environmental conservation as well as enjoy gardening in the city's limited space. Ecosystem-based approaches draw the attention of the DRR (Disaster Risk Reduction) scholars to response to the extreme disaster events worldwide (Renaud et al., 2013). Such an ecosystem based approach can be vertical gardening. It is a type of gardening that grows upward (vertically) using a trellis or other support system rather than horizontally. Ecosystem-based approaches identify three distinct strengths: they are (1) environmentally sustainable, (2) cost effective, and (3) socially and economically responsible.

Background of the Study

Urbanization in Dhaka City is increasing at a very fast rate which creates several problems leading to deteriorate basic rights of the citizens. Though urbanization brings along economic and social benefits, it has

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some negative effects. One of the worst negative consequences of rapid urbanization is the degradation of the urban environment on a massive scale, of the kind which is now experienced in Dhaka. Air, water, soil of the city has been polluted to dangerous levels. The eco-system services fall into shortage due to the pollution of the environment caused by rapid urbanization. In response to this problem, our study will evaluate the effectiveness of vertical gardening in Dhaka City. We will examine the services that a vertical garden provides and its contribution in solving urban problems such as environment pollution, noise pollution, carbon footprint, heat wave etc. An in-depth investigation on the implications of vertical gardening will be carried out in a particular area of Dhaka city to identify the opportunities and associated challenges.

Research Aim

- To explore in what ways vertical gardening offers services and support to maintain ecological sustainability and reducing disaster risks in the context of Dhaka city.

Research Objective

- To produce a map of eco-system services from vertical gardening.
- To understand the relation between eco-system services and urban resilience.
- To identify challenges and opportunities of vertical gardening.

Literature Review

Vertical Gardening

Vertical gardening is an agricultural technique, used in high-rise buildings that enables to produce large scale food production by controlling and without controlling the environmental conditions based on technologies, hydroponics and cutting-edge greenhouse methods (Abel, 2010). Rooftop gardening is the most popular and effective practice of vertical gardening. Extensive and intensive are the two types of green roof system. Extensive green roof system has some basic characteristics. They are light-weight; need low maintenance, its average soil depth 5-15cm (2-6 in). So rooftop would have the capacity to bear the weight 70-170kg/sq (14-35 lb. /sq.) if someone want to cultivate this type of rooftop gardening. Generally mosses and herbs are planted in this type of garden. On the other hand Intensive green roof system needs deep soil depth, wide plant range and high capital cost. The average soil depth in the intensive green roof system is ranging from 20-60 cm (8-24 in) and rooftop needs the capacity to bear 290-967.7 kg/sq ft. (60-200 lb. /sq.). Trees and shrubs are planted this type of gardening (Mowla, 2010). China, Japan, Holland, South Korea, Italy, Canada, USA and Singapore already adopted this method to produce more crops and safe their environment (Sivamani, Bae, & Cho, 2013).

Eco-system Services and Urban Disaster Risk Management

From the very beginning of human life, human depends on goods and services from nature for survival. Eco-system in the nature can play a vital role for providing eco-system services. It can help climate regulation, water supply and purification, cycling of water and nutrients (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). There are four types of eco-system services. Provisioning services (e.g. food, fresh water), supporting services (e.g. nutrient cycle, water cycle), regulating services (e.g. climate regulation, erosion regulation) and cultural services (e.g. Spiritual and religious values, knowledge system, sense of place) (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005).

Vertical farming can control storm water run-off. Plants of the garden can capture and hold the heavy rain water. Then it can absorb and release the water in the atmosphere through evaporation and evapotranspiration (Banerjee & Adenaauer, 2014). Plants in the vertical farming can hold about 70-90% of the precipitation that occurs in the summer. And in winter it can hold about 25-40% of precipitation (Hossain, 2009). Over all precipitation which occurs throughout the year, plants of the rooftop garden retain 50-90% of rainwater (Mowla, 2005). Plants of vertical garden can be used as a shade in the building from solar radiation. Plants can cool down the surrounding environment using their evapotranspiration process and reduce temperature (Afrin, 2009). Rooftop gardening can reduce cooling cost up to 50% and it can reduce about 25% of the surrounding temperature (Specht et al., 2014). But these process are depended on some factors like building size and location, climatic condition of that areas and type of the rooftop garden (Mowla, 2005).

Methods

In this research, we took 15 samples. It was depending on types of vertical gardening. There are three types of vertical gardening that exist in Mirpur DOHS area. For each type we took 5 respondents and in total it is 15. Qualitative study ordered through in-depth interviews with the help of open ended, semi-structured questionnaire.

Study Area Selection

To conduct this research, Mirpur DOHS has been selected as the study area. We have selected Mirpur DOHS as our study area, because the area has existence of vertical gardening practitioners. The area is urbanized hence there is a huge supply of roof space. And no studies have been conducted in this area on this concept before.

Data Collection Tools

Both primary and secondary data were collected for the study. In this study we consider three types of data collection methods for primary data collection. 1) Interview, 2) Participant observation, and 3) Visual documentation. 15 practitioners were interviewed to explore their motivation, types of plants grown, cost of maintenance, benefits and problem faced and other experiences. A questionnaire was prepared which included open ended questions. We observed the types of gardens during field visits and we have seen that in general there were 3 types of vertical gardening methods namely- 1) intensive, 2) semi intensive, 3) extensive. There were mostly 4 types of plants which include various species of - 1) fruits 2) flowers 3) vegetables and 4) ornamentals. One exceptional type that we found was the cultivation of different species of spices. Images were captured during field visits taking the permission of the respondents to keep permanent record of direct observations. Secondary data were collected from literature review. Various secondary information and data were used in this paper which was collected from research articles, newspapers, internet, books and journals.

Data Analysis Method

In our study we used thematic analysis. Why we used thematic analysis? As we conducted a qualitative research, this method helped us to explain the data in an easier way. We turned our quantitative data into qualitative form through this analysis method. We can easily organize our information using this method.

Result

Practicing types of vertical gardening

In Mirpur DOHS area we have found three types of vertical gardening. Existing three types of vertical gardening are A) Intensive vertical gardening B) Semi-intensive vertical gardening and C) Extensive vertical gardening. In Dhaka city, practices of intensive vertical gardening are rare. But in Mirpur DOHS area, scenario is totally different. Including intensive, three types of gardening are available in most of the buildings. They did special treatment on their building rooftops; as a result they can practice the intensive one as well as other types. In Photograph 1 we can see one of the intensive vertical gardens which are practiced in the study area. Generally using 7 – 24+ inches deep soil with a saturated weight increase of 35 - 80+ lbs/ft² in their rooftop for preparing intensive one. They are planting Banana, Mango, Coconut, Jackfruit and Papaya in their intensive garden. In this case, maintenance cost is little bit higher than other types. In the semi-intensive vertical gardening, people are using 5-7 inches deep soil and increase the saturated weight of 25-35 lbs/ft² in their rooftop. They are using some selected perennials, sedums, ornamental grasses, herbs, little shrubs and small tree for preparing this type of vertical gardening. From Photograph 2 we can see the scenario of the semi intensive vertical gardening in the study area. Different kinds of vegetables like hyacinth bean, cucumber, bottle gourd, ribbed gourd, sponse gourd, wax gourd and bitter gourd are cultivating as semi-intensive plants. Photograph 3 represents the extensive type of vertical gardening. In this type soil depth is ranging from 2-5 inch and increase the load of 14-35 lbs/ft² in the rooftop (Mowla, 2010). Respondents are using 3-5 inches deep soils that increase the saturated weight of 15-25 lbs/ft² in their rooftop. Generally most of the species of flowers, ornamentals, spices and some species of vegetables are planted as extensive type of vertical gardening in the study area. In Mirpur DOHS area people are practicing mixed types of vertical gardening. We did not find any rooftop that practices single type of vertical gardening. For cultivating fruits, they prefer intensive vertical gardening. For cultivating vegetables most of the times they prefer semi-intensive vertical gardening and prefer extensive type for planting flowers, ornamentals and spices.

Figure 1: Types of vertical gardening in the study area.

Source: The authors (Field Survey, 2018)

Ecosystem Services

Table 1: Eco-system Services of vertical gardening in the study area.

Benefits of Vertical Gardening	Eco-system Services			
	Provision	Regulate	Cultural	Support
Storm water quantity		Water		
Storm water quality	Water	Purification		Nutrient cycling
Genetic resources	Seeds			
Heat island		Climate		
Building energy		Climate		
Noise reduction		Sound	Aesthetic	
Air pollution reduction		Air		Nutrient cycling
Temperature reduction		Climate		
Waste management		Waste treatment		
Biodiversity		Pollination	Knowledge	Nutrient cycling
Retard fire			Well-being	
Views			Aesthetic	
Social cohesion			Well-being	
Mental satisfaction			Spiritual well-being	
Vertical agriculture	Food		Educational	Soil formation
Education opportunity			Educational	
Improvement of health condition			Well-being	
Cognitive development and knowledge preservation			Knowledge	
Employment opportunity			Well-being	
Carbon sequestration		Air		

Source: The authors (Field Survey, 2018)

Provisioning Services

Food, freshwater, timber, fibers, medicinal plants obtained from ecosystem are provisioning services (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005). Eco-system services supply for three types of provisioning services i.e. forage, timber, fisheries (Balvanera et al. 2014). Field observation showed the cultivation of various vegetables, fruits, flowers, aromatic and medicinal plants that takes place on the terrace of individual plots. It could be observed that gardeners maintain soil fertility by adding manure and compost with a view to enhancing food production. Some gardeners use kitchen wastes as fertilizer to produce chemical free fruits and vegetables.

Supporting Services

According to The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA, 2005), ‘maintenance of soil fertility’ is considered as supporting service, which help to generate other ecosystem services, e.g. the production of food. We found that gardeners use organic wastes to maintain the soil fertility of their gardens. They mentioned vertical gardening as a refuge for many species of birds, bees, and butterflies. Well- designed green roofs can provide habitat for different species.

Regulating Services

Almost all the interviewed gardeners emphasize on the importance of soil fertility. They identified ‘local climate regulation’ which is understood as urban cooling. As an important benefit from vertical gardens, pollination was only mentioned by some of the interviewers. Pollination was mainly related to flower and ornamental plants. The formation of soil organic matter by flora and fauna and the enrichment of soil fertility through legumes (nitrogen fixation) were recognized. The scientifically undisputed importance of ‘pollination’ as supporting service for ‘food supply’ and ‘biodiversity’ (Andersson et al., 2007) remained undefined by many gardeners. Other remaining regulating services ‘local climate regulation’, ‘air purification’ were often described as feelings and related to an increased well-being through nature exposure in vertical gardens.

Cultural ecosystem services

The production of food in vertical gardens is supporting manifold other ecosystem services though most of them are cultural ecosystems services described as the most important services provided by vertical gardens. Field observation has shown that ecosystem services have provided a fulfillment in social cohesion & integration, nature & spiritual experiences (Tidball’s 2012). Each and every gardener firmly stated vertical gardening as a means of mental recreation, including ‘aesthetical information’, ‘relaxation & stress reduction’, and ‘entertainment & leisure’ across all garden types. Respondents said that active engagement in gardening activities and exposure to nature creates a source of mental relaxation. Local climate regulations are contextualized among benefits for mental recreation by gardeners.

Opportunity for Vertical Gardening in the Context of Dhaka City

In traditional farming, only one crop can be produced at a time. But in vertical gardening different kinds of products can be produced at the same time. This is the key difference between vertical gardening and traditional gardening. As our horizontal space is decreasing day by day we should go for vertical expansion as early as possible.

Recycling of Organic Waste

Organic wastes which are generated from household can be used as a fertilizer in the vertical garden. We have found that many respondents are using organic wastes in their garden. This process is eco-friendly and do not causes water contamination like chemical fertilizer does. Recycled organic wastes turn into fertilizer for our garden. So there is no need to spend extra money for buying chemical fertilizers. From Table 2, we can see 4 respondents are using their organic waste in their garden as a fertilizer. This is almost one third of the total respondents

Table 2. Types of fertilizer which are used in vertical gardening

Types of fertilizer	No. of respondent
Chemical Fertilizer	5
Organic waste	4

No fertilizer are used	6
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Source: The authors (Field Survey, 2018)

Local Job Opportunities

Vertical gardening can create direct or indirect job opportunities for jobless people in the cities. In Mirpur DOHS area some people are working permanently and some other working temporary in the vertical gardening of the respondents. From Table 3 we can see 4 respondents who have one permanent employee whose salary is 9-12 thousand BDT. On the other hand temporary employee works on daily basis. They take the salary 500 BDT per day. Rest of 4 respondents has no employee. They themselves work in their garden. In this way vertical garden can create job opportunity for the local people.

Table 3: Types of employment and number of employee

Types of employment	Number of employee	Salary (BDT)	No. of respondents
Permanent employee	01	(9-12 thousand) per month/person	4
Temporary employee	01	500 per day	7
No employee	none	None	4

Source: The authors (Field Survey, 2018)

Improved Food Security

In our Dhaka city we have limited access or no access to fresh food. Access to available food and access to fresh food are the two different terms. To produce available fresh food people are practicing vertical garden in their rooftop. Respondents cultivate vegetables, fruits and flowers in their rooftop to reduce the dependency of fruits and vegetables in the market which are contaminated with poisonous substances. Price is another factor which influences them to do vertical gardening.

Challenges for Vertical Gardening in the Context of Dhaka City

- The roofs need to be cleaned on a regular basis as the leaves of the plants make the roof unclean. The respondents said that if proper cleaning measures are not taken then it can become an ideal breeding ground for mosquitos and other insects.
- Another problem that was unveiled from the respondent's interviews was about not getting desirable production and not being able to communicate easily with experts regarding the problems they face while practicing gardening.
- When asked about the cost it was found that it was not an issue for those who can afford it. A reasonable set up cost is required apart from that and the maintenance cost is pretty much affordable.
- There is no government intervention or authority to take care of the gardens. The building owners, guards, caretakers (often known as Mali) and sometimes part-time staffs are assigned to take care of the gardens.
- Lack of technological knowledge is also a constraint for practicing vertical gardening. There are very few opportunities for acquiring technological and cultivation knowledge.
- Green roofs are heavier and as such, require more structural support to be implemented. The structure and weight of a roof garden can cause problems for the overall building.

Discussion

Air pollution, sound pollution, carbon emission, urban heat island and water logging are becoming serious urban disaster risks in last few decades. Through evaporation and evapotranspiration it absorbed and released the water in the atmosphere. In summer vertical gardening hold about 70-90% of the precipitation. All the precipitation that occurs throughout the year, it holds 50-90% of rainwater (Mowla, 2005). Vertical gardening can reduce the effect of urban heat island. Vegetation can be used as a shade for building and cool down the surrounding environment by using their evapotranspiration process. Vertical gardening can reduce the cooling cost up to 50% and 25% of the surrounding temperature (Specht et al., 2014). Growing medium of the vertical gardening can reduce the lower sound frequencies on the other hand plants can reduce the higher sound frequencies. Depending on the types of vertical garden, it can reduce sound by 46-50 decibels (Afrin, 2009).

It is well known that trees, shrubs and other natural vegetation affect urban air contaminant levels. Air quality and the overall experience of health and well-being of humans living in urban areas are also affected by these. In response to urban environmental problems some authors have studied the effects of vegetation, particularly trees, on cooling ambient urban air, shading buildings and absorbing gaseous air contaminants. Green-house gas emission added a new dimension in the concept of urban disaster risk. Buildings in the city area like Dhaka, consume about 48% of all energy (Besthorn, 2013). So buildings are responsible for emitting green-house in the urban area. Vertical gardening in the rooftop can cool down the buildings and reduce the buildings' heat consumption.

In terms of urban resilience we consider four parameter of resilience. Parameters are economic, social, infrastructural and environmental (Merrow et al., 2016). In terms of eco-system services there are four types. Provisioning, cultural, supporting and regulating are the urban eco-system services (Bolund and Hunhammar 1999). We show how eco-system services which are generated from vertical gardening can contribute to establish urban resilience. First, provisioning services are food, fuel, genetic resources and fresh water, which come from urban agriculture (Bolund and Hunhammar 1999). By producing seasonal and non-seasonal foods, it can reduce the urban food insecurity. Practicing vertical gardening can ensure available access to fresh food for city dwellers. Creating local job opportunity, it can support local economy. Then cultural services (Spiritual and religious values, Recreation and aesthetic values) develop our mental health and increase our social cohesion (Bolund and Hunhammar 1999). It can help to create better social bonding among the people. Social resilience mainly focuses on some factors like quality of education and information, health access and emphasize on social relationship. Supporting ecosystem services develop the social infrastructure. By practicing vertical gardening we can mitigate the consequences of urban deforestation (Lovell and Taylor, 2013). We actually conserve our forest practicing through this way. We can use organic wastes in our vertical garden as fertilizers. In this way, we can manage our wastes very easily. Waste management itself a big problem in our country as well as outside the world. Regulating services is the most important one which can control or regulate the urban disaster risk (Bolund and Hunhammar 1999). Vertical gardening can hold the rain water and reduce the possibility of water logging in the urban area. It can absorb the dust particles and clean the polluted air. It is working like an insulator and reducing the consequence of sound pollution.

Conclusion

Yet for a significant implementation of the practice of vertical gardening, additional steps can be suggested like, vertical gardening needs more demanding structural standards. Roofs of the existing buildings need to be checked before adoption of vertical gardening whether those can bear the load of vegetation or not. Dying and unhealthy plants may have a negative impact on those observing them. Special attention should be given in appropriate plant selection and correct placement in the garden. Use of chemical must be prohibited as it may have detrimental effects on the health of the people. Adoption of organic fertilizers, mulching, hand weeding, companion planting and adequate spacing of plants etc. can reduce the necessity of using chemicals. Maintenance of drainage system is another most important fact in vertical gardening. Incorporating a drainage layer with a water storage layer below it can work as a reservoir for plants that can draw upon dry weather. In future research regarding this field, researchers can focus on the infrastructural issue. We only discuss how vertical gardening can reduce the urban disaster risk. But it has a great influence in climate change factor. So future research can be on how vertical gardening reduces the climate impact in urban area and to what extent it can do that. The cost benefit analysis of vertical gardening in the context of social, economic and environmental sector could be a better finding.

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